

The Effect of Work Stress and Work Environment on Work Spirit through Discipline Work in the Service of Population and Civil Registration District Labuhan Batu

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ABSTRACT: An organization in carrying out its activities to achieve the desired goals needs good management, especially human resources. Human resources are the main capital in planning, organizing, directing and driving factors that exist within a company. Good human resource management is expected to be able to produce optimal performance for the organization. This study aims to determine whether work stress and work environment affect employee morale through work discipline as an intervening variable at the Labuhanbatu District Education Office . The research was conducted on 36 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a significant effect between work stress on work discipline , 2) there is a significant effect between work environment variables on work discipline , 3) there is a significant effect between work stress variables on morale , 4) there is a significant effect between work environment variables on work morale , 5) there is a significant influence between work discipline variables on work morale , 6) work discipline variables cannot influence work stress variables on morale , 7) work discipline variables cannot influence work environment variables on morale.

KEYWORDS: Work Stress, Work Environment, Work Discipline, Work Morale.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important asset for the organization , which essentially functions as a driving factor for every activity within the company. An organization in carrying out its activities to achieve the desired goals needs good management, especially human resources. Human resources are the main capital in planning, organizing, directing and driving factors that exist within a company. Good human resource management is expected to be able to produce optimal performance for the organization .

Good performance will facilitate the organization in achieving its goals. Research conducted by Bechtold (2010) states that one of the factors that influence performance is morale. High morale will have a positive impact on the organization, whereas low morale will harm the organization such as high absenteeism, employee turnover, and low productivity (Zendy, 2012)

Morale can be interpreted as a sort of succinct statement of the various psychological forces that exert pressure in connection with one's work. Morale can also be interpreted as a climate or working atmosphere in an organization that shows a sense of enthusiasm in carrying out work and encourages employees to work better and more productively.

The Department of Population and Civil Registration of Labuhanbatu Regency is a regional government agency of Labuhanbatu Regency which is engaged in population and civil registration. The services provided are related to resident registration documents such as electronic ID cards, family cards, and transfer documents, KIA (Child Identity Cards) as well as civil registration documents such as birth certificates, marriage certificates, death certificates and others.

There are problems that occur in the Population and Civil Registration Office of Labuhanbatu Regency , namely the morale of employees who are still low in carrying out their daily work. This is caused by the demands of work that must be completed in a short time, besides that the amount of workload and time given is not in accordance with the ability of the employee, causing stress for the employee. This also causes employees to be unenthusiastic at work so that employees become negligent and undisciplined at work.

Based on the phenomena that occur in the Department of Population and Civil Registration of Labuhanbatu Regency, the researcher is interested in conducting a study related to this phenomenon with the title " **The Effect of Work Stress and Work Environment on Work Enthusiasm through Work Discipline in the Department of Population and Civil Registration of Labuhanbatu Regency**" .

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Spirit

Every organization always tries to increase the work productivity of its employees. Therefore, leaders need to find ways to raise employee morale. This is an important problem, because work enthusiasm reflects a deep pleasure in the work being done so that work can be completed more quickly and can also achieve better results and ultimately there is an increase in the work productivity of these employees (Agustini, 2011: 58).

Meanwhile, according to Agustini (2011: 63) the factors that influence morale are as follows:

1. Concerning satisfaction outside of work such as income, a sense of security, and the work environment.
2. Concerning satisfaction with work, namely work interest, opportunities for advancement, prestige in the organization, and awareness of responsibility towards work.
3. Concerning personal satisfaction such as employee pride in their work, feelings of being well cared for, and the ability to get along with fellow employees.

Work Discipline

Agustini (2011: 72) work discipline is the awareness and willingness of a person to comply with all applicable social rules and norms.

According to Sutrisno (2011: 97) there are 4 (four) indicators of work discipline, including:

1. Obey the rules of time.
2. Obey company regulations. .
3. Obey the rules of conduct at work.
4. Comply with other regulations in the company.

Work Stress

Stress is usually defined by internal and external conditions that create stressful situations, and the symptoms are experienced by everyone who is depressed, (Ivanko, 2012: 88).

The indicators of work stress according to (2012:12) are as follows:

1. Individual Stress
Includes: role conflict, career burden, career development, work relationships.
2. Organizational Stress
Includes: Organizational structure, leadership.

Work environment

The work environment is one important factor in influencing employee performance. In working employees must be supported by a good working environment situation. A good work environment is one that is safe, peaceful, clean, not noisy, bright and free from all kinds of threats and distractions that can hinder employees from working optimally.

According to Alhusin (2017: 34) the work environment is an environment in which employees work, while working conditions are conditions in which the employee works.

Wursanto (2009:124), indicators of the non-physical work environment are:

1. Supervision. Supervision is carried out continuously using a strict system.
2. Work atmosphere. A work atmosphere that can provide encouragement and enthusiasm for work.

- Treatment. Treatment is good, humane, not equated with robots or machines, relationships are harmonious, informal and get fair treatment.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of Labuhanbatu Regency which is located at Jalan Meranti Number 1 Rantauprapat, Padang Matinggi Village, Rantau Utara District, Labuhanbatu Regency. The population in this study were all permanent employees (PNS) at the Labuhanbatu Regency Population and Civil Registration Service, which were recorded in December 2022, totaling 36 people. Due to the small number of population, the sampling technique in this study is a saturated sample, which means that the total sample uses the entire population. This research is included in the associative research approach quantitative. This study examines the relationship between the variables Job Stress (X₁) and Work Environment (X₂) to the variable Morale (Y) and Work Motivation (Z) as the intervening variable. In this study the approach used is approach quantitative because the data used to analyze the influence between variables expressed by numbers or a numerical scale (Kuncoro, 2011, in Wulandari, 2015).

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

A. Sobel Test

Testing the mediation hypothesis can also be carried out with a procedure developed by Sobel and known as the Sobel test (Sobel test). The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence X to Y through Z, as follows:

$$Z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{(b^2SE_a^2 + a^2SE_b^2)}}$$

Where:

a = regression coefficient of the independent variable on the mediating variable

b = regression coefficient of the mediating variable on the dependent variable

SEa = standard error of estimation from the influence of the independent variable on the mediating variable

SEb = standard error of estimation of the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable

The following are the results of the Sobel test with the variable work stress on morale through work discipline .

$$t = \frac{0.201 \times 0.109}{\sqrt{(0.109^2 \times 0.144^2) + (0.201^2 \times 0.147^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.201 \times 0.109}{\sqrt{0.00024636441 + 0.0008730252}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.021909}{0.00111938961}$$

$$t = 19,572$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, a t value of 19,572 is obtained, so that the t value is 19,572 > t table 3,209 . It can be concluded that the work discipline variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of work stress and morale.

The following are the results of the Sobel test with work environment variables on work enthusiasm through work discipline .

$$t = \frac{0.106 \times 0.109}{\sqrt{(0.109^2 \times 0.267^2) + (0.106^2 \times 0.147^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.106 \times 0.109}{\sqrt{0.00084687768 + 0.00024279872}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.011554}{0.0010896764}$$

$$t = 10.603$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, a t value of 10,603 is obtained, so that the t value is $10,603 > t$ table 3,209. It can be concluded that the work discipline variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of the work environment on morale .

B. Path Analysis Sub Model II

Referring to the output of the Model II regression in the table section, it can be seen that the significance values of the three variables are: Work Stress (X1) = 0.000 , Work Environment (X2) = 0.012 , Work Discipline (Z) = 0.051 . These results conclude that the regression of Sub Model II, namely the variable Work Stress (X1) and Work Discipline (Z) has no significant effect on morale (Y). But the work environment variable (X2) has a significant effect on work morale (Y). The value of R2 or R Square contained in the Model Summary table is 0.252 , this shows that the contribution or contribution to the influence of Work Stress (X1), Work Environment (X2) and Work Discipline (Z) on Work Morale (Y) is 58 % , while the remaining 42 % is contributed by other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, the value of e2 can be found using the formula $e^2 = \tilde{\alpha} (1 - 0.252) = 0.864$. Thus the path diagram of the structure model II is obtained as follows:

Effect of Job Stress on Work Discipline

work stress variable has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at Disdukcapil, Labuhanbatu Regency . The work stress variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.201 and has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the work stress variable will add to the work discipline value of Disdukcapil Labuhanbatu Regency employees by 0.201 per one unit score

The Effect of the Work Environment on Work Discipline

work environment variable has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at Disdukcapil in Labuhanbatu Regency. The work environment variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.106 and has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the work environment variable will add to the work discipline value of Disdukcapil Labuhanbatu Regency employees by 0.106 per one unit score.

The Effect of Work Stress on Work Morale

Figure 4.9 Sub Model II Path Diagram

The results of the analysis show that the direct effect of work stress (X1) on morale (Y) is 0.025 . Meanwhile, the indirect effect of work stress (X1) on morale (Y) through work discipline (Z), namely $0.201 \times 0.091 = 0.018$. Then the total effect given by the Job Stress variable (X1) on Work Morale (Y) is the direct effect plus the indirect effect, namely $0.025 + 0.018 = 0.043$. Based

on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the direct effect value is 0.025 and the indirect effect is 0.018 , which means that the direct effect value is greater than the indirect effect value. These results indicate that indirectly the variable Work Stress (X1) through Work Discipline (Z) does not have a significant effect on Morale (Y).

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence of the work environment (X2) on morale (Y) is 0.091 . Meanwhile, the indirect effect of the work environment (X2) on morale (Y) through work discipline (Z), is $0.106 \times 0.109 = 0.011$. Then the total effect given by the Work Environment variable (X2) on Work Morale (Y) is the direct effect plus the indirect effect, namely $0.091 + 0.011 = 0.102$. Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the direct effect value is 0.091 and the indirect effect is 0.011 , which means that the direct effect value is greater than the indirect effect value. These results indicate that indirectly the variable Work Environment (X2) through Work Discipline (Z) does not have a significant effect on Morale (Y).

Table 4.17 Total Influence Value

No.	Influence	Direct Influence	Indirect Influence	Total Impact
1	X1 → Y	0.025 _	$0.201 \times 0.091 = 0.018$ _	0.043 _
2	X2 → Y	0.091 _	$0.106 \times 0.109 = 0.011$ _	0.102 _

CONCLUSION

- Work stress has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at Disdukcapil, Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that the level of work stress can affect employee discipline .
- The work environment has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at Disdukcapil, Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that a comfortable work environment can improve employee work discipline .
- Work stress has a positive and significant effect on morale at Disdukcapil, Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that the level of work stress can affect work spirit .
- The work environment has a positive and significant effect on morale at the Disdukcapil in Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that a comfortable work environment can increase employee morale .
- Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on morale at the Disdukcapil in Labuhanbatu Regency. This means that this condition proves that the better the employee's work discipline, the higher the morale will be .
- The influence of work stress on the morale of Disdukcapil employees in Labuhanbatu Regency will be smaller if done through work discipline . The direct effect of work stress on employee morale is greater than the indirect effect of work stress on morale. It can be concluded that work discipline is not able to mediate the effect of work stress on morale .
- The influence of the work environment on the morale of Disdukcapil employees in Labuhanbatu Regency will be smaller if done through work discipline . The direct effect of the work environment on morale is greater than the indirect effect of the work environment on morale . It can be concluded that work discipline is not able to mediate the influence of the work environment on morale .

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